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Pathways

Proteins

Cytochrome P450

Microbial metabolism in diverse environments

GABA receptor

DNA polymerase

Nucleoside diphosphate kinase
Solute carrier family

Biosynthesis of secondary metabolites

Purine metabolism

Pyrimidine metabolism

Caffeine metabolism

Sulfur metabolism

Phenylalanine metabolism

Nicotinate and nicotinamide metabolism

Biosynthesis of antibiotics

Enzymes

UDP-glucuronosyltransferase

DNA polymerase

Tryptophan metabolism

Drug metabolism – other enzymes

Fructose and mannose metabolism

Tyrosine metabolism

Arachidonic acid metabolism

Polymethoxymycin receptor

Arginine and proline metabolism

Steroid hormone biosynthesis

Toluene degradation

ABC transporter

Glycosaminoglycan degradation

cytochrome P450 Metabolism of

Xylene degradation

antigen

Styrene degradation

xenobiotics by cytochrome P450

Propionate metabolism

nitroalkaloid synthesis